

TYPES OF NON-TRADITIONAL LESSONS

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Annotation: this article provides detailed information about the methods of teachers' use of pedagogical technologies in music education classes, the use of non-traditional lessons in the effective organization of lessons, non-traditional types of lessons.

Keywords: music, lesson, pedagogical technology, teacher, lesson, culture, traditional lesson, dance, demand, theory.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada musiqa ta'lim darslarida o'qituvchilarning dars o'tishda pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish usullari, darslarni samarali tashkil etishda noan'anaviy darslardan foydalanish, noan'anaviy dars turlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, dars, pedagogik texnologiya, o'qituvchi, dars, madaniyat, an'anaviy dars, raqs, talab, nazariya.

Аннотация: в данной статье представлена подробная информация о методах использования педагогами педагогических технологий на занятиях по музыкальному образованию, использовании нетрадиционных уроков в эффективной организации уроков, нетрадиционных типах уроков.

Ключевые слова: музыка, урок, педагогическая технология, учитель, урок, культура, традиционный урок, танец, потребность, теория.

Currently, due to the demands of our time, non-traditional types of lessons are entering the musical education system. We have developed several non-traditional types of lessons that can be used in music education based on existing pedagogical technologies. Now we will comment on each type of lesson.

[1]

Concert lessons - practical application of all musical and theoretical knowledge of students, assessment of their own and others' knowledge, learning to behave on stage, formation of skills of singing as a team and soloist, playing on children's musical instruments. It provides ample opportunity perform dance elements, etc. It is advisable to organize such classes mainly at the end of one quarter and the beginning of another. Because in this type of lesson, students perform a "concert" based on the songs they have learned during the quarter. Such lessons provide a wide opportunity to determine and evaluate the level of knowledge of students.[2] The lesson is planned in advance. Pupils prepare the songs they have learned. The teacher must have assigned a task to each student in the previous lesson. Lessons begin with everyone singing the national anthem

together. These lessons are important because students use all their creative abilities and performance skills. Such lessons lay the foundation for the formation of students' musical taste and musical outlook. In addition, students develop the skills of self-control on stage, artistry, singing as a team, independence, and initiative.

Before the lesson, the teacher tells the students what songs to sing and what songs to play after which, the lessons are organized based on a specific system and following the rules. In such lessons, the teacher has the opportunity to evaluate almost all students. Coming to the "concert" classes dressed in accordance with the content of the songs will increase the interest of the students and increase the effectiveness of the lesson. Students should be given the opportunity to use their existing knowledge and talents in concert lessons. For example, someone sings well, someone prefers dancing, someone has strong acting skills. It is necessary for the teacher to organize a concert taking into account the wishes and possibilities of each student. Concert lessons can be dedicated to the birthday or work of a composer or writer. In this concert, the works created by this artist will be performed in the class, and the teacher or one of the students will talk about the life and work of the author.

Quiz lessons are mainly conducted in the process of listening to music. The teacher plays music to the students with the help of some technical means. Students, in turn, will find the name, performer, composer of this music. Such lessons are very useful when the topic "Composer, performer and listener" is taught. [3]

In quiz lessons, the teacher divides the students into lines, that is, into teams. Points are awarded based on the activity of each team and the correct answers. Quiz lessons can be used in the process of not only listening to music, but also singing. In this, students are taught to have certain concepts about the creators-composers, poets and performers of musical works. Such lessons can be adapted to each subject. For example, when a teacher teaches students the music of neighboring nations, listening to the music of different nations and peoples and determining which nation they belong to will develop the students' musical perception. [4] They learn to distinguish the music of other nations from each other. Also, their musical outlook is formed. Quiz lessons lay the foundation for the formation of musical taste, musical perception and musical outlook.

Debate lessons - in-depth analysis of musical works, knowledge of music literacy - music history, music literature, analysis of a musical work, musical

form, etc. will be aimed at strengthening the theoretical knowledge. This type of training is mainly based on musical-theoretical knowledge gained during a quarter or half a year. Debate classes are organized based on students' previous knowledge. It is considered a class organized for the purpose of explaining the impossible issues, coming to a consensus on controversial views, and on this basis, achieving independent acquisition of knowledge by students, forming musical thinking, musical perception, and musical culture.[5] Debate classes differ from other classes in their specific aspects, that is, in these classes there is a dispute over a certain issue. The teacher and students share their opinions. In such classes, the debate is strong, and each point is supported by its evidence, and the most appropriate option is accepted.

Debate classes require a lot of preparation from students. These lessons provide students with a foundation for present-responsibility, independent thinking, creative approach to events, deepening of their speech.[6] Students in the class get different impressions from one musical piece. Therefore, sharing their thoughts and opinions will enrich their thinking and imagination.

Debate classes are also of great pedagogical importance. It is one of the important tools for educating students' aesthetic feelings. The topic of the discussion is chosen by the teacher from the point of view of its compatibility with the content and requirements of the curriculum, as well as with the age characteristics of the students. It is necessary to take into account the wishes and interests of students. The teacher prepares controversial questions and invites students to debate. The teacher activates the students with questions and helps the students to be consistent and clear in their answers. Debate lessons create a foundation for students' speech to be clear and fluent, and to develop their communication skills. The organization of such lessons brings the teacher and students closer to each other, creates a friendly relationship, and increases the efficiency of mastering musical-theoretical knowledge. The organization of such lessons requires teachers and students to follow a number of the following rules during the lesson:

From students:

- 1) to express one's thoughts clearly and without haste;
- 2) to be respectful to the interlocutors during the discussion;
- 3) maintaining etiquette (raise your hands and answer in turn);
- 4) not giving halal when other students are speaking;
- 5) listen carefully to the opinions of interlocutors;
- 6) not to deviate from the topic;

- 7) striving to participate in the discussion, even if the opinion is wrong;
- 8) to prove one's opinion with evidence.

From the teacher:

- 1) engage students in discussion;
- 2) to interest students;
- 3) explaining and correcting students' mistakes;
- 4) putting students' thoughts into one system;
- 5) encourage those who actively participate.

The main purpose of the fun and clever lesson is to test the knowledge of the students in the lessons, to strengthen them, to control the knowledge acquired outside the lesson, to direct them to a specific goal, to form the students' communication with musical works. The organization of the lesson in the form of a competition allows you to get to know the work of the studied composer or the history of the creation of a musical piece. In such lessons, it is also important to understand the skills of composers, the musical tools embedded in the essence of their works, to make them interested in mastering, and to accustom them to independent observation. Forming the qualities of activity, ingenuity, ingenuity, vigilance in students is also a component of the purpose of this lesson.

The fun and clever lesson is one of the non-traditional forms of lessons that ensure an interesting passage of musical lessons and active participation of students. The fun and the smart class can be held in several directions. Repeating the topics covered, organizing various didactic games in the form of singing, question-and-answer, identifying musical instruments, interpreting the content of listened musical works, and memorizing works. can be.

The abilities of a child participating in music lessons develop in the process of musical activity. It is the duty of music educators to properly organize and direct this development, taking into account the young psychological characteristics of children. For example, if a child is not taught to distinguish the pitch of sounds from early childhood, he will not be able to perform tasks that younger children can easily perform by the age of seven.

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